

Complexes of 5-Phenyl-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazole with some Bivalent Metal Ions

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Complexes of 5-phenyl-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazole (HPMT) with the metals (M) Ni^{II}, Pd^{II}, Pt^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} of the formulae M(PMT)_n.nH₂O (n=0 or 2) have been prepared and characterised by magnetic, conductance, uv and ir spectral data.

INCREASING physiological importance of nitrogen and sulphur donor organic compounds¹ and active role played by certain metal ions coordinated to them² have interested us in synthesising and studying the structural aspects of the metal complexes with some sulphur and nitrogen donor ligands³⁻⁵. The present paper reports the complexes of 5-phenyl-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazole (HPMT) with Ni^{II}, Pd^{II}, Pt^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II}. HPMT can coordinate to metal ions in thione (I) or thiol (II) form either as a neutral or mono-anionic (PMT) molecule.

Experimental

The ligand HPMT was prepared by the reported method⁶. The metal salts used were either AnalaR or 'extra pure' (S.M.) grade.

Preparation of complexes :

$M(\text{PMT})_n.n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M=\text{Ni}^{II}, \text{Pd}^{II}, \text{Pt}^{II}, \text{Zn}^{II}, \text{Cd}^{II}, \text{Hg}^{II}$ or Pb^{II} ; $n=0$ or 2): An aqueous ethanolic solution of the hydrated metal chloride (0.005 mol in 50 ml; acetate in case of Pb^{II}) was mixed with hot ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.012 mol in 50 ml) and pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted to 7-8 by adding aqueous sodium acetate. The resulting solid complex separated was digested on a steam-bath, filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried in an air-oven at 90-100°.

$M(\text{HPMT})_2X_2$ ($M=\text{Cd}^{II}$ or Hg^{II} ; $X=\text{Cl}$ or Br): An ethanolic solution of the metal halide (0.005 mol in 60 ml) and ligand (0.01 mol in 100 ml) was mixed while hot. The resulting dihalo complex was either separated on cooling or concentrating to a small volume. The solid products was filtered, washed with cold ethanol and dried in air.

The molar conductance (in DMF), magnetic susceptibility and reflectance spectra of the complexes were recorded as reported earlier^{3,4}. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. The results are shown in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The analytical results (Table 1) indicate that in alkaline medium (pH > 7) HPMT is deprotonated and coordinates as a monoanionic ligand yielding inner bischelates $M(\text{PMT})_2.n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($n=0$ or 2) with Ni, Pd, Pt, Cd, Hg and Pb, whereas in acidic or neutral medium (pH < 6) it coordinates as neutral molecule forming dihalo complexes $M(\text{HPMT})_2X_2$ ($X=\text{Cl}$ or Br) with Cd and Hg. The complexes are almost insoluble in water, but dissolve appreciably in DMF. The molar conductance values in DMF (Table 1) indicate the non-ionic nature of the complexes. The complex $M(\text{PMT})_2.2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ does not lose water molecules below 120° which indicates that these are coordinated or strongly held in the crystal lattice.

As expected Zn, Pd, Pt, Cd, Hg and Pb complexes are diamagnetic and do not display electronic reflectance band in the visible region. The diamagnetism of Pd and Pt complexes indicates their planar structure. The room temperature magnetic moment value of $\text{Ni}(\text{PMT})_2.2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=3.42$ B.M.) lies in the range displayed by tetrahedral or distorted octahedral complexes^{10,11}. The electronic reflectance spectrum of $\text{Ni}(\text{PMT})_2.2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ shows five bands in the region 24 500-10 000 cm^{-1} . The spectral pattern is similar to that of the distorted octahedral Ni^{II} complexes^{12,13} and hence these bands are assigned accordingly: 24 500s, charge transfer ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$; 22 580m, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g^0$; 16 580m sh, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}$; 11 080w, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$; and 10 060w, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g^2$ transition. The reflectance spectra of the other complexes do not display distinct electronic bands in visible region.

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TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)			Λ_M^* $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		M	N	Cl/Br	
Ni(PMT) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	Yellowish brown	12.32 (12.19)	11.58 (11.64)	—	7
Zn(PMT) ₂	Cream	14.51 (14.46)	12.56 (12.39)	—	3
Cd(PMT) ₂	Cream yellow	22.81 (22.52)	11.37 (11.23)	—	3
Hg(PMT) ₂	Light yellow	33.88 (34.16)	9.63 (9.54)	—	4
Pb(PMT) ₂	White	35.04 (34.89)	9.31 (9.42)	—	2
Cd(HPMT) ₂ Cl ₂	Yellowish white	19.75 (19.65)	9.78 (9.79)	12.52 (12.39)	10
Cd(HPMT) ₂ Br ₂	Yellowish white	16.93 (17.01)	8.43 (8.47)	23.98 (24.18)	12
Hg(HPMT) ₂ Cl ₂	White	30.53 (30.39)	8.21 (8.48)	11.12 (10.74)	15
Hg(HPMT) ₂ Br ₂	White	27.21 (26.78)	7.23 (7.48)	21.68 (21.33)	13
Pd(PMT) ₂	Red	21.10 (21.57)	11.03 (11.36)	—	7
Pt(PMT) ₂	Dirty yellow	33.12 (33.54)	9.41 (9.63)	—	5

*At 30–1°.

Considering the stoichiometry, Zn, Cd, Hg and Pb complexes M(PMT)₂, Cd(HPMT)₂X₂ and Hg(HPMT)₂X₂ are tentatively suggested to possess four-coordinated tetrahedral structure since tetrahedral stereochemistry is the preferred arrangement for these metal ions¹⁴.

Ir spectra : The absence of ν_{SH} band at 2400–2600 cm^{-1} of the ligand indicates that the ligand is present mainly in thione form. The ν_{NH} band of the ligand (3245 cm^{-1}) disappears in M(PMT)₂ (M=Zn, Cd, Hg or Pb) indicating deprotonation of the coordinated ligand. In Ni(PMT)₂·2H₂O, a broad band at ~3400 cm^{-1} is attributed to ν_{OH} of the water molecules. In the dihalo complexes the ν_{NH} band is not affected appreciably which indicates that the ligand coordinates as a neutral molecule.

The ligand HPMT possesses potential thioamide group (NH–C=S) and the thioamide bands^{4-6,15-18} are affected appreciably in M(PMT)₂·nH₂O complexes. The thioamide band-I (1548 cm^{-1}), band-II (1366 cm^{-1}) and band-III (1182 cm^{-1}) shift to higher frequencies by 20–60 cm^{-1} whereas the thioamide band-IV (942 cm^{-1}) shifts to lower frequency by 230–240 cm^{-1} indicating the involvement of both nitrogen and sulphur of the thioamide group in bonding, i.e. bonding of the thioamide group is in the spectral form $(\text{N}=\text{C}=\text{S})^{16-18}$

In Cd(HPMT)₂Cl₂ and Hg(HPMT)₂Cl₂, there is little change in thioamide bands I, II and III, however the red-shift of thioamide band-IV by

30–40 cm^{-1} indicates the bonding of the ligand only through thione sulphur in these complexes.

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